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Abbracciando Tutti: Embracing All

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Abstract: The title of Pope Francis's 2020 encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, is very exclusive in its language though inclusive in its content. Many women in India as well as across the globe objected to the words *fratelli* and fraternity as they signal an insensitivity to the concerns of women and the signs of the time, which call for use of inclusive language and respect for the dignity of women and all persons. However, the text in itself is all-embracing and encouraging, as it exhorts practicing love, kindness, dialogue and sensitivity to transcend the borders of geography and distance and create bridges of friendship, equality, subsidiarity and solidarity. Embedded in the text is the clarion call

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to embrace all, '*abbracciare tutti*,' which requires respecting the

dignity and rights of women and others and giving them greater opportunities and protection. The article thus explores these themes in upholding peace, harmony, equality and the common good of all.

Keywords: Gender Equality, Solidarity, Friendship, Bridges, Universal Communion, Dialogue.

Introduction

While the title of Pope Francis' encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* (FT) is misleading in that it refers only to 'All Brothers', the content is all inclusive, integral as well as incumbent.

Hence, this article is titled '*Abbracciando Tutti*' from '*abbracciare tutti*,' which the pope himself uses twice in the Italian text of the encyclical (3, 60). Interestingly, the corresponding word 'embrace' occurs eight times in the English text. Using the gerund forms, *abbracciando* and embracing, implies an inherent urgent call to embrace all as brothers and sisters, beyond the constructed boundaries of class, caste, culture, gender, religion, language, space, distance and so forth. 'Embracing All' does not mean seeing and treating everyone the same but acknowledging and respecting each one's uniqueness and diversity. It is thus a more comprehensive and conducive mandate, challenging everyone to have a mind and heart that is open to all, that welcomes all, that can love and serve all, so as to enjoy universal communion and companionship. This was what was proclaimed by Pope Francis and the Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb when they met in Abu Dhabi: "God has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters" (FT 5). If men and women are created equally in the image and likeness of God, why is it then that many women and those of other sexual orientations are looked at and treated so differently from men? Why are most women vulnerable

to abuse, oppression, exploitation, and domestication? What is needed to restore the dignity, equality, and freedom of all persons? It is possible needed to restore the dignity, equality, and freedom of all persons if we uphold the vision of embracing all, which requires a move toward gender equality, building bridges, creating friendships and establishing solidarity. We find these themes developed by Francis in *Fratelli Tutti*.

1. From Gender Biases to Gender Equality

Sex and gender are often used interchangeably and even though attempts have been made to define and describe the terms, there is still confusion with the terminology and usage of the words. From the 1990s, sex began to be seen as a continuum based on biological and genetic differences while gender was considered as a combination of the personal recognition of one's sexual orientation and how one desires to be recognized by others. Thus, while sex refers to the biological characteristics that distinguish humans as female, male or other, gender is an acquired identity that is learned, changes over time, and varies widely within and across cultures. One's gender identity is determined by social and cultural norms and expectations and is influenced by psychological, economic, political, religious, and environmental factors. Sexism refers to gender stereotyping of men and women as hierarchically ordered (men over women). It enforces certain characteristics and roles for men and women on the basis of their biological differences, thereby excluding women from certain positions, places and privileges. Sexism is expressed in conventional images of women and men, exclusive language, sexist symbols, images and even advertising strategies. Sexism leads to unequal roles and relations among men and women; unequal values assigned to tasks and work; unequal access to resources, power and decision making. Sexism leads to all forms of violence and crimes against women including rape, kidnapping and abduction, dowry deaths, cruelty by husbands and relatives, molestation, sexual harassment, trafficking, physical, mental and

emotional abuse. Violence is a way to assert power and is often used to silence women and others on the margins if they attempt to change the prescribed order of things.

In 1993, India ratified the Convention on Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination against women (CEDAW), and on 2nd April 2013 the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act 2013 was passed to ensure speedy trial in cases of sexual assault. The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013 came into effect on 9th December 2013 to ensure safety and protection of women at work and this was later followed by the “CBCI Guidelines to deal with Sexual harassment at workplace” on 14th September 2017, a thirty-page document issued by the Catholic Bishops Conference of India. Despite these Acts and the enforcement of laws, policies, and reservations in favour of women in the church and society, the position of women in the home, workplace, socio-cultural and religious institutions, has not changed much in the Indian context. Although there is an improvement in literacy, employment opportunities and health care for women, gender disparities, exploitation and abuse continue to affect women at all levels. They are most susceptible to being exploited economically, politically, socially, culturally and sexually. The Gender Policy of the Catholic Church in India affirms that “in most socio-cultural communities in India, women’s human rights are limited by religious, cultural and traditional practices that are based on patriarchal norms” (Gender Policy, 2010, 2).

There is thus a strong need for gender equality by which all persons can have the freedom and right to make their own choices and develop their potential to the fullest. The International Labour Organization in 2000 defined Gender Equality as:

the concept that all human beings, both men and women, are free to develop their personal abilities and make choices without the limitations set by stereotypes, rigid gender roles

and prejudices. Gender equality means that the different behaviours, aspirations and needs of women and men are considered, valued and favoured equally. It does not mean that women and men have to become the same, but that their rights, responsibilities and opportunities will not depend on whether they are born male or female.

The hallmark of gender equality is found in Paul's letter to the Galatians (3:28), where there is to be no discrimination on the basis of religious ethnicity, socio-political conditions and biological differences (Schüssler Fiorenza, 2001, 115). In recognizing that women have fewer rights mainly on the basis of their sex, Francis holds that women must not be excluded or denied a dignified life (FT 121).

While women and men are categorized differently according to socio-cultural constructions of gender, it is known that gender is not the only factor responsible for discrimination and oppression. There are diverse interwoven processes, layers and intersections of sex, gender, caste, class, race, religion, ethnicity, language and age that are responsible for the differing discriminations among people and even among women as a category. The term intersectionality was introduced to reveal the "reciprocally constructing phenomena" such as class, caste, gender, and race, that govern power relations and social inequalities (Collins, 2015, 2).

Intersectionality is a powerful framework to understand and analyse the complexity and multiple intersecting structures of power and discrimination that constitute and affect people.

Though intersectionality as a tool for analysis has become widely used in the twenty-first century in many disciplines, the idea of intersecting oppressions was already in use in India from the 19th century onwards by Savitribai Phule and her husband Jyotirao Phule who fought against caste, class, gender, economic and religious discriminations. (Collins and Bilge, 2016, 3-4). However, there is not much published on their lives and their great contribution since they belonged to

the lower caste. If gender equality is to be achieved in India, a substantial shift is needed from the intersectionality of oppressions to an inclusive interconnectedness that can embrace all persons and the entire ecosystem.

2. From Borders to Bridges

Borders or boundaries, in demarcating spaces, can either connect with others or create distances. It is not just about physical borders, but mental, emotional, psychological, and even spiritual borders that can prevent an encounter with persons, communities, cultures, and nations. Francis rightly notes that in the world today “the sense of belonging to a single human family is fading, and the dream of working together for justice and peace seems an outdated utopia. What reigns instead is a cool, comfortable and globalized indifference, born of deep disillusionment concealed behind a deceptive illusion: thinking that we are all-powerful, while failing to realize that we are all in the same boat” (FT 30). It is disconcerting at times to see the growing indifference, individualism and inhibition leading to indignity and isolation. It is only love, according to Francis, that can shatter the chains that keep people “isolated and separate” since love “builds bridges”, “exudes compassion and dignity” and “enables us to create one great family, where all of us can feel at home” (FT 62).

We are constantly invited to cross the borders that distance people and bridge the social, spatial, cultural, and religious divides. Thinking through the implications of such transitions requires a dynamic and creative theological and moral imagination – a renewed way of perceiving and imagining persons, cultures, religions, and traditions. We need new modes of knowing, new ways of being, and new processes of functioning in accordance with the mind and heart of Jesus Christ for our present context, time, and culture. The

incarnation was a border crossing event where Jesus crossed all borders to become one among us, so that he could bridge the gaps between humans and between humanity and God. As followers of Jesus, we are called to be open to engage in dialogue, create processes of mutual encounter, reach out to one another, and build bridges of love, compassion, forgiveness, and reconciliation (FT 203, 217).

While Francis considers forgiveness and reconciliation as central themes in Christianity and other religions, he clarifies that it is not about condoning an oppressor or “renouncing our own rights” (FT 237). Rather, extending love and forgiveness to an oppressor “means seeking ways to make him cease his oppression; it means stripping him of a power that he does not know how to use, and that diminishes his own humanity and that of others” (FT 241). In building bridges of compassion, “those who suffer injustice have to defend strenuously their own rights and those of their family, precisely because they must preserve the dignity they have received as a loving gift from God” (FT 241). The Church thus has an urgent mission to break down divisive and destructive borders, to build walls and to “sow seeds of reconciliation,” if it is to love and embrace everyone (FT 276). Respecting the integrity of each person, we can engage in dialogue with people of diverse religions, cultures, regions, and languages, and work together to eradicate the oppression and exploitation of women and other marginalized persons.

3. From Fragmentation to Friendship

A consumeristic culture with its focus on development and advancement leads to more production than what is required, using more than is needed, a use and throw mentality, dehumanization, and destruction of things. The rights of the poor and the marginalized, especially women and girls, must thus be safeguarded against the vested interests of the multinational corporations (MNC’s) that are controlling the market economy.

The Church in India through its creative use of media and communication can counter the advertisements and strategies employed by the MNC's that manipulate national interests and plunder the natural resources of the country. A model of mastery leads to fragmentation and alienation in contrast to the mystery model in which we are called to discover the common space in which each tradition, religion and culture finds its full identity.

Fragmentation can arise from disappointment caused by “unrealistic expectations,” exploitation from “unscrupulous traffickers,” abuses, xenophobia, separation of children from their parents who migrate (FT 39). Fragmentation is also from distancing, division and disregarding justice and human rights. The poor and marginalized continue to be oppressed and shunned, used and abused as objects of scorn, robbed of their human dignity and worth. Women are doubly poor as they have to often “endure situations of exclusion, mistreatment and violence, since they are frequently less able to defend their rights” (FT 23). During the Covid-19 pandemic women had to bear the most brunt of loss of jobs and working from home. Besides the stress from the double burden of working and managing the home, quite a few women had to put up with domestic violence, physical, verbal and emotional abuse and increase of demands from their husbands and children. The shared spaces of the home became like prison cells with no outlet for women to go out and meet other women.

There is a necessity for interpersonal encounters of kindness, dialogue, mutual listening and care for one another. For Francis, when “the dignity of the human person is respected, and his or her rights recognized and guaranteed, creativity and interdependence thrive, and the creativity of the human personality is released through actions that further the common good” (FT 18). What is needed is a sense of responsibility for all brothers and sisters, a creative openness

to the ‘other’, and protection for the rights of all persons (FT 40). With regard to migrants, Francis urges people to “welcome, protect, promote and integrate” them, thereby undertaking a journey together (FT 129). Embracing everyone on the basis of one’s shared humanity is from a universal command to love, which seeks the best for others and involves “a social friendship that excludes no one and a fraternity that is open to all” (FT 60, 94). Francis sees the importance of social friendships and a universal openness in love which goes beyond the borders of one’s family, community, and region to embrace anyone in need and thus expand one’s circle of friends (FT 96, 99). Genuine social friendships and universal fraternity enhance dignity, equality and freedom acknowledging the “worth of every human person, always and everywhere” (FT 103, 106).

Human Dignity, which is the key foundational principle in Catholic Social teaching (CST) sees humans as the *imago Dei*. The dignity and uniqueness of human beings as created in the image and likeness of God consists in their intimate relationship with God, which also implies a close relationship with other humans and with all of creation. Pope John Paul II in his Post-Synodal Apostolic Exhortation, *Ecclesia in Asia*, urged the Church in Asia to commit herself socially and pastorally to uphold the dignity of the human person and in particular to maintain the dignity, freedom and human rights of women since they are most discriminated against and treated as commodities (EA §33b, 34). He also emphasized the need for women to be given more opportunities to participate actively in the life and mission of the Church. This finds an echo in the preamble of the Constitution of India where justice (social, economic and political), liberty (of thought, expression, belief, faith and worship), equality (of status and of opportunity), and fraternity (assuring the dignity of the individual and the unity and integrity of the nation) are to be upheld and secured for all. However, social stratification marked by gender, race, class and economic status continue to affect the health and well-being of women and other persons on the margins of society.

In order to heal the fragmentation, brokenness and suffering that women and men continue to experience, we need to understand and accept the Trinitarian mystery of God which is a relationship of love, communion, equality and mutuality with no superiority, subjugation or domination. It is in community that we can learn to respect, appreciate, love and care for every person and everything and thus work together towards communion and harmony. Communion and harmony in the Indian tradition encompasses all of reality and can be experienced in the encounter of different cultures, regions and religions. The search for harmony in India is connected to “a worldview that is organic, interactive and cosmic;” one that seeks to promote life, wellbeing and happiness (Tirimanna, 2007, 111). While harmony in India is challenged by socio-political, cultural, economic, religious and ecological factors there is need for mutuality and collaboration not just to do away with conflicts, but to bring forth life and goodness. Communion and harmony do not dissolve hierarchy or positions, but it is possible to acknowledge and celebrate diversity and difference, collaborating with each other for a common vision as modelled in the Trinity.

For Elizabeth Johnson (1992), the Trinitarian symbol evokes deep communion among persons which makes for transcending binary categories such as male-female, master-slave. It indicates a genuine relationship of mutuality, radical equality and community in diversity with no domination or subordination but an encompassing of loving and liberating compassion. This communion or *perichōrēsis* signifying a revolving, cyclical movement manifests the intermingling and interweaving of persons and things (Johnson, 220). Such interconnectedness can enable humans to relate to others (within the family, workplace and society), to God and to all of creation, in a healthy and holistic manner so as to establish peace, harmony, communion and friendship despite any fragmentation.

4. From Self-Centredness to Solidarity

The Covid-19 pandemic has brought to our realization the fact that selfishness and self-centredness cannot thrive. This view is affirmed by Pope Francis who points out that we have become aware that “we are a global community, all in the same boat, where one person’s problems are the problems of all,” and since “we are brothers and sisters of one another,” it is presumed that “we can only be saved together” (FT 32). He also holds that the injustice in the world is due to a “[c]onsumerist individualism”, by which since “persons come to be viewed simply as obstacles to our own serene existence, we end up treating them as annoyances and we become increasingly aggressive” (FT 222). This type of “[r]adical individualism is a virus that is extremely difficult to eliminate” as it “makes us believe that everything consists in giving free rein to our own ambitions, as if by pursuing ever greater ambitions and creating safety nets we would somehow be serving the common good” (FT 105).

Self-centredness and individualism create rifts and boundaries through indifference and isolation. There is a narrow pre-occupation with one’s own interests and the concerns of one’s family, community, region and social group. It creates an in-group and out-group where the outsider is sometimes even viewed as a threat. Francis considers that “[c]losed groups and self-absorbed couples that define themselves in opposition to others tend to be expressions of selfishness and mere self-preservation” (FT 89). There is a tendency to hoard wealth, share less with others, and take and save more than one needs.

To counter self-centredness, Francis emphasizes the value of solidarity, which as a “moral virtue and social attitude”, expresses itself concretely in service, care for others especially the most vulnerable, “thinking and acting in terms of community,” and most of all, “combatting the structural causes of poverty, inequality, the lack of work, land and housing, the denial of social and labour rights” (FT 115-116). Solidarity is related to the foundational principles of human dignity, subsidiarity and the

common good. Thus, while working in solidarity, there can be subsidiarity at all levels to work for the common good of promoting the sustainability and flourishing of all persons. Solidarity creates shared spaces for co-responsibility, interdependence, and a sense of belongingness. A sense of solidarity can help to bring about a “universal consciousness and mutual concern,” which is so necessary in caring for persons and our common home (FT 117). This sense of solidarity must be first cultivated in the family where “the values of love and fraternity, togetherness and sharing, concern and care for others are lived out and handed on (FT 114).

Solidarity with the poor and marginalized and a commitment to respect the dignity and rights of all persons is a constant plea in the Church documents. Solidarity, for Pope John Paul II, “helps us to see the ‘other’ - whether a person, people or nation - not just as some kind of instrument, with a work capacity and physical strength to be exploited at low cost and then discarded when no longer useful, but as our ‘neighbour’, a ‘helper’ (cf. Gen 2:18-20), to be made a sharer, on par with ourselves, in the banquet of life to which all are equally invited by God” (*Sollicitudo Rei Socialis* §39). Francis goes further to look at a global ethic of solidarity “shaped by interdependence and shared responsibility in the whole human family” (FT 127, 146). This alone can lead to lasting peace, openness, welcome, concern for others and the common good Francis also thinks that the current forms of communication and proper use of digital media and the internet which offer “possibilities for encounter and solidarity” must be encouraged (FT 205). There is also an urgent need to cultivate solidarity across borders, regions, and nations so as to put an end to all forms of intersecting oppressions and discrimination created by colonialism, capitalism, patriarchy and social stratification and promote the flourishing of all persons.

Samuel Rayan (2011) sees in Micah 6:8 (“what does the LORD require of you but to do justice, and to love kindness, and to walk humbly with your God”) a program for embracing life by envisioning a renewed human community with an authentic spirituality. This spirituality consists in upholding love, justice and equity for everyone by challenging and subverting the systems and structures that have led to oppression and dehumanization of persons and destruction of the universe. It thus invites us to dream of a new world order where there is love, justice, peace, equality and solidarity.

Conclusion

The vision of *Abbracciando Tutti* or Embracing All, is one in which differences among persons, communities, movements and nations must be overcome to make room for people of different classes, races, social stratifications, religions and languages. This will allow all to live together, serve each other and work in solidarity and love to ensure dignity, equality, freedom, communion, harmony, justice and peace for all. In *Fratelli Tutti* Pope Francis rightly asserts that Covid-19 has taught us that “our lives are interwoven with and sustained by ordinary people valiantly shaping the decisive events of our shared history: doctors, nurses, pharmacists, storekeepers and supermarket workers, cleaning personnel, caretakers, transport workers, men and women working to provide essential services and public safety, volunteers, priests and religious,” and hence we need to embrace everyone as brothers and sisters and work towards “peace, justice and fraternity,” adopting a culture of dialogue as the path, mutual cooperation as the code of conduct and reciprocal understanding as the method and standard” (FT 54, 285).

How can we envisage this way forward of ‘Embracing All’ persons from different cultures, spaces and religious traditions with dignity, equality, freedom and harmony in the shared orchestra of life? Chitranina Ravikiran’s proposed concept of *melharmony*, projected to guide the use of harmony in modal music, can be used to symbolically represent this renewed vision.

Carnatic music is “one of the most colorful, complete and highly melodic systems of the world” according to Robert Morris and Chitravina N. Ravikiran (2006, 255). It focuses on “permutations of successive notes,” giving “equal importance to melody, rhythm, and lyrics,” placing “equal emphasis on composition and improvisation,” and combining “grace and force in adequate proportions.” It has “72 seven-tone scales,” with each scale as a “living entity capable of evoking or communicating emotions.” The theory of *melharmony* is “melody with harmony and chords that conform to the modal/scalar, sequential and ornamental principles of highly evolved melodic systems,” in which the leading voice at the same time is to be “derived from the melodic and combinational structure of the raga.” A raga in Indian music is a melodic scale or sequence of music notes in “a specific combination and permutation in both ascent and descent” (Morris & Ravikiran, 2006, 255). While Western music has tones in equal temperament and scales with four values (diminished, minor, major and augmented) or three values (diminished, perfect and augmented), Carnatic music postulates multiple chromatic values. Indian music thus has the potential for many combinations and styles. While “most ragas are neither equivalent nor reducible to Western common practice keys or modes,” it must be noted that “the issues of Western counterpoint and voice leading are intrinsic to melharmonic practice since Western music’s harmony grew out of the modal monophony of the Middle Ages and the progression of chords and their hierarchies are still based on melodic principles” (Morris & Ravikiran, 2006, 274). Thus, “melharmony is not about imposing harmony on modal music, but about preserving and enhancing a mode’s melodic identity in its harmonization” (Morris & Ravikiran, 2006, 274).

Is it possible to move forward from an envisioned world of harmony to a conceptual universe of *melharmony* with its echo reverberating locally as well as globally? While sacred

scriptures, traditions and structures are significant and need to be preserved, we need to see how can they be reinterpreted, reconstructed and reclaimed for the present context to enhance the human dignity of all persons for a melharmonious universe without borders, biases and selfish egoism. As Virgilio Elizondo (2008, 28) notes:

Borders will not disappear, differences will not fade away but they need not divide and keep peoples apart. Rather than being the fences of separation they can well serve as the reference points....

Rather than seeing them as the ultimate dividing line between you and me, between us and them, we can see borders as the privileged meeting places where different persons and peoples will come together to form a new and more inclusive humanity. Rather than viewing them as the ultimate chaos of mixture, impurity and disorder, we can begin to see them for what they truly are: the cradles of the new humanity.

Borders separate but they can also connect. They thus have the potential to build bridges and renew humanity although in reality it can be quite difficult and demanding. Borders even though they can never be fully dissolved, can serve as spaces for encounter, dialogue, communion and transformation. As Elizondo rightly attests, it is in the encounter with the other that we can be a source of revelation to each other, enabling new identities to emerge through the painful process of birthing and dying. This dying to a rigid exclusive position that one tends to have over religion, culture, beliefs, values, doctrines and so on is challenging and risky, but also much needed to build bridges of equality, friendship, communion and solidarity. It is only through genuine openness, engagement, reflection and dialogue that we can recognize the uniqueness and beauty of our own identity as well

as that of others and relate to each other with dignity, equality and freedom.

For true conversion to take place, we must be ready to allow God to touch us and heal us and make us whole. It is only then that we will put on the mind and heart of Jesus and see the world as sacrament and sacred. We will be able to experience God in everything and everything in God, thus being true *contemplatives in action*. Raimundo Panikkar's (Panikkar and Eastham, 1993, 55) *cosmotheandric vision* which is an extension of the Trinitarian mystery sees all of reality as a meaningful whole in communion that leads to equality and mutuality with no superiority, subjugation and domination. This "envisioning of all of reality in terms of three worlds," the divine, the human and the cosmos, is "an invariant of human culture, whether this vision is expressed spatially, temporally, cosmologically or metaphysically" (Panikkar and Eastham, 55). The three dimensions of reality coexist with each other in such a way that "they are neither three modes of a monolithic undifferentiated reality, nor three elements of a pluralistic system;" rather they are "one, though intrinsically a threefold, relation which manifests the ultimate constitution of reality" (Panikkar and Eastham, x). The *cosmotheandric vision* thus surmounts dialectical and binary relations by looking at the "trinitarian structure of everything," so as to stress the "intrinsic relationship" among the three dimensions of reality. It is an attempt to recover the "positive middle way between the paranoia of monism and the schizophrenia of dualism" (Panikkar and Eastham, 59).

For Panikkar, "the need for a unified vision of reality is all the more urgent since there are already many other unifying factors at work which may bring about a partial unification, but which ignore fundamental ingredients of the human being and consequently do violence to reality" (Panikkar and Eastham, 12). Rather than a global universal perspective which privileges one story or one truth, what is needed is an

open horizon, which is not closed up “in any single perspective, vision or system.” An open horizon enables us to cross the boundaries of our imagination and perception to discover and encounter the mystery in the other. The awareness of the “ever-elusive character of any horizon and its constitutive openness” (Panikkar and Eastham, 13), enables humans to relate to others (within the family, workplace and society), to God and to all of creation, in a healthy and holistic openness so as to establish peace, harmony and communion.

Despite the manifold borders and the interweaving of spaces over time, places and cultures, the all-encompassing *cosmotheandric vision* thus offers the hope and possibility of creating friendships and sacred spaces that cut across tradition, culture, religion, caste, race, gender and language so as to retrieve and reclaim the original state of belongingness and relatedness that all humans, whether rich or poor, citizens or strangers, black or white, can share as persons created in the image and likeness of the Triune God. Only then in true freedom, wholeness and ultimate meaning can we respond appropriately to the miseries of our time, and in particular to the fragmentation and brokenness that women and others on the margins experience. In learning to respect, appreciate, love and care for the beauty and value in everyone and everything, we can to some extent restore human dignity and work together for the common good of all, across any borders.

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QUOTES FROM FRATELLI TUTTI

*“Nor can we fail to mention that seeking and pursuing the good of others and of the entire human family also implies helping individuals and societies to mature in the moral values that foster integral human development...Even more, it suggests a striving for excellence and what is best for others, their growth in maturity and health, the cultivation of values and not simply material wellbeing. A similar expression exists in Latin: *benevolentia*. This is an attitude that ‘wills the good’ of others; it bespeaks a yearning for goodness, an inclination towards all that is fine and excellent, a desire to fill the lives of others with what is beautiful, sublime and edifying” (FT 112)*

“Even when affronted, goodness is never weak but rather, shows its strength by refusing to take revenge” (FT 226)

*“Nowadays, what do certain words like democracy, freedom, justice, or unity really mean? They have been bent and shaped to serve as tools for domination, as meaningless tags that can be used to justify any action”
(FT 14)*